

REVIEW OF THE CONCEPT OF OER AND THE CONNECTION WITH THE CONCEPT OF DISTANCE LEARNING

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Abstract. This article analyzes the reforms of higher education, which began to change dramatically around the world in the 1990s, and its necessity for fundamental changes in society. It is mentioned that the changes in the education system of Uzbekistan due to independence were modeled on the European environment. Also, the concept of Open educational resources and the introduction of distance education elements were analytically analyzed and a conclusion was presented.

Key words: *higher education, reforms, globalization, National Research Area, to online lectures, IT, research, implementation.*

The modern system of higher education in the world in the period from the 90s of the twentieth century until today are faced with many pressures of globalization and expansion in the development of information and communication technologies. In such circumstances, it is inevitable that there have been significant changes in the European system of higher education. The main changes relate to the introduction of precise criteria for the accreditation of the university, faculty, and academic programs

and orientations, as well as the introduction of criteria and rules for quality control in higher education. Parallel to this process, perfected their skills and approaches in creating a syllabus a specific cases, methods of teaching, and methods of evaluation of students' activities, bearing in mind the pre-exam and the exam.

Among the goals of the our country is the creation of a national knowledge society, which rests on two pillars – National Research Area and the Uzbekistan's Higher Education Area. Their implementation has a strategic place in European integration.

Things that have opened the door to changes in the mode of teaching, or the manner of presentation of course content, and led to the displacement of traditional lectures to online lectures are expansive development, implementation and wide availability communication technologies. In fact, there is no area of life and work in which IT resources are not enabled better communication, planning and implementation of all activities of vital importance for modern man.

In an era of rapid increase the volume of global knowledge, information technology has enabled the continuous modernization approach to both teaching in higher education in world level and accelerated implementation, customization and implementation of the systemlice of distance learning. Thus, under the influence of modern technical and technological achievements and aspirations of modern man that activity in the private and business sphere into line with the opportunities that largely provides the technology, the system of education, especially higher education system in recent years has been actively involved in the eld of IT support to the teaching process. Modern education, namely, includes introducing multimedia systems, distance learning, virtual schools, and other information technology that supported modes of communication between teachers and students, which lead or may lead to

an increase in the activities of students, better evaluation of their knowledge and advancement in accordance with individual abilities and prior knowledge.

Distance learning as a modern approach to teaching is significantly associated with the concept called Open Educational Resources – OER established at international level, which means that “all teaching and research materials, as well as learning materials available to the public and put into circulation with the licence open source, which allows people their release multiple use, access, and distribution with or without partial restriction (Report of the Tempus project Baektel, 2014, p. 4). Distance learning is a relatively newer model of learning supported by information and communication technologies certainly bring new opportunities in learning and teaching. The most important role in this is the development of the Internet, which allows not only remote access to teaching materials, but in addition seamless communication between teachers and students, and in cases where they are located in remote locations. However, with the advent of this approach in teaching, there were numerous conflicting opinions about the significance and purpose of the virtual mode of communication in relation to the classical lectures.

At the beginning of the paper, it was pointed out that the expansive development of information technology greatly facilitates the acquisition and exchange of knowledge and information.

The term Open Educational Resources (OER) first was used at the UNESCO conference in 2000 as a means to allow release access to educational resources on a global level (Report of the Tempus project Baektel, 2014, p.5). According to the views of many authors, OER movement originated from developments in open (free) learning, distance learning and the broad context of a culture of open learning, open source, free sharing and many others who have appeared at the end of the 20th century

(Wiley 2006; Wiley, 2007; Mossley, 2013). In its primary form, the concept of OER describes each educational resources (including the curriculum, teaching materials, a variety of applications that include multimedia content as well as any material that is manufactured to be used for teaching and learning) which is freely available for the use of students and teachers, but not limited to companies in the form of payments for the use of, or payment of fees for licences.

How important is the use of OER by the fact that the National OER's record increase of users, the majority of this number is calculated from several hundred thousand registered users and up to several million. In the USA the number is much higher. In Central Asia, the OER inserted into the Strategy of Higher Education by 2020, which is based on the openness of Education.

Based on the research of application of OER in higher education in the universities of the European Union comes to the conclusion that there are a number of initiatives in the eld of higher education in the European Union (both by organizations and by individuals) relating to the promotion of public education available globally community learning and teaching. Some of these initiatives are: Open Education Central Asia, which was used by the European Commission, as part of a continental consortium of publicly available educational programs; Miriada X, which was launched in the National University of the Uzbekistan; iMOOC, which was launched in Europe; Future Learn as a branch of the Open University and forum, which were launched in the world. From the above-mentioned initiatives in the eld of higher education in the Central Asian relating to the promotion of OER, it is clearly evident that the Distance Learning System as integral part of the concept of Open Educational Resources, respectively platforms that enable the realization of the concept of Distance Learning is actually an integral part of instruments and tools of

promotion and realization of the concept of OER. On this point, it is important to mention one of the most famous and successful initiatives to promote and implement the concept of Distance Learning System, and thus the concept of OER. It is a Open Learn initiative.

However, in the context of the relations between OER and Distance Learning System, Butcher points out that OER and Distance Learning System are not synonymous, but many people make the mistake of just identifying the two terms. Open licenced content can be producing in any type of media in the form of text on paper, video or audio clip, or in multimedia form. Many courses within the concept of learning can be conceived in the form of OER, but that does not mean that every online learning automatically OER concept. On the contrary, many of the material within the OER, are solded not only through online, but are printed in hard copy and are available to users. Bearing in mind what kind of all the challenges facing developing countries, it seems increasingly that they prefer to use printed materials in relation to the placement of materials designed for e-learning.

When we mentioned a Open Learn initiative, we can say the following. The Open Learn is well-known institutional source of HE OER. The Open University is one of the most successful universities for Distance Learning System in the world. Strive to be the world leader in the design, content and delivery of open learning and distance learning through academic research, pedagogic innovation and partnership. Materials with the Open University courses are available free on the website Open Learn. Users can and hundreds of release lessons within twelve different areas, each with a forum for discussion. OpenLearn offers arrange of methods and strategies in order to form a society of teachers and students around his content. It is composed of

two parts: Learning Space that offers learning materials and LabSpace where content can be downloading, reorganize, adjust and re-use.

After a brief review of the concept of OER and the connection with the concept of Distance Learning System, it is necessary to make a brief overview of the importance of application of OER in education, as well as on the situation in Serbia in the eld of opportunities for the implementation of the concept of Open Educational Resources. In support of the implementation of OER in education, especially in the eld of higher education highlights the following.

The most important reason for the use of OER is the fact that it is a learning (educational) resource with an open licence, which has high potential to contribute in improving the quality and effectiveness of learning. Transformative educational potential of OER revolves around three related perspectives:

1. Increase the availability of high quality, relevant learning resources can contribute to increased productivity of students and teachers. Since OER removes all restrictions on copying resources, can reduce the cost of access to educational materials. In many systems, the payment of royalties on textbooks and other educational materials represent a significant part of total costs, and procedures for obtaining permission to use copyrighted material may require a lot of time and money.

2. Principle permits adaptation of the material has enabled one of many mechanisms for creating the role of students as active participants in the education process. Students achieved the best result in learning not only passively reading and absorbing, but when practical work and create. Allowed access to he content that encourages activity and creativity of students through multiple use and adaptation of

that content can have a significant contribution to the creation of more efficient learning environment.

3. OER can build capacity by providing institutions and educators release or favourable access to the necessary resources to improve their skills in creating teaching materials and implementing the necessary instructional design that would allow the integration of such materials in high quality learning programs.

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